

Northern Ireland Good Friday Agreement

Date Signed: 10 April, 1998

Accord Type: Comprehensive Peace Agreement

Country: United Kingdom

95.24

Implementation Score after 10 years

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PROVISIONS IN THIS ACCORD

Cease Fire
Powersharing Transitional Government
Constitutional Reform
Inter-ethnic/State Relations
Electoral/Political Party Reform
Decentralization/Federalism
Dispute Resolution Committee
Judiciary Reform
Police Reform
Demobilization
Disarmament
Reintegration
Prisoner Release
Paramilitary Groups
Human Rights
Right of Self-Determination
Citizenship Reform
Women's Rights
Education Reform
Official Language and Symbol
Minority Rights
Reparations
Economic and Social Development
Ratification Mechanism
Detailed Implementation Timeline
Independence Referendum
Review of Agreement
Verification/Monitoring Mechanism

Paramilitary Groups

Implementation Timeline

About this Provision

Year	Implementation
1998	Intermediate Implementation
	The Good Friday Agreement required all paramilitary to cease their activities and maintain ceasefire. While decommissioning of weapons in possession of the IRA remained a main obstacle to the peace process until 2005, the IRA resorted to ceasefire and disbanded itself. The Ulster Defense Association/Ulster Freedom Fighters and Ulster Volunteer Force also resorted to ceasefire and did not participate in any paramilitary activities. They ceased paramilitary activities.
	The Continuity Irish Republican Army, the Loyalist Volunteer Force, the Irish National Liberation Army and the Real Irish Republican Army were recognized as terrorist groups, and their commitment to ceasefire was not recognized as they were involved in ceasefire violations after the ceasefire announcement in 1997.[fn]"Paramilitary Groups Across the Divide", <i>BBC News</i> , accessed 1 February 2013, http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/events/northern_ireland/paramilitaries/69824...
1999	Intermediate Implementation
	No further developments observed.
2000	Intermediate Implementation
	No further developments observed.
2001	Intermediate Implementation
	No further developments observed.
2002	Intermediate Implementation
	No further developments observed.
2003	Intermediate Implementation
	No further developments observed.
2004	Intermediate Implementation
	No further developments observed.
2005	Intermediate Implementation
	No further developments observed.
2006	Intermediate Implementation
	No further developments observed.
2007	Intermediate Implementation
	No further developments observed.

Please always cite: ["Annualized implementation data on comprehensive intrastate peace accords, 1989–2012."](#) Madhav Joshi, Jason Michael Quinn, and Patrick M. Regan. *Journal of Peace Research* 52 (2015): 551-562.

